

A NOTE ON THE FREE ENERGY OF NUCLEATION AND LIMIT OF SUPERSATURATION

BY A. C. CHATTERJI AND R. P. RASTOGI

Experimentally observed supersaturation limits have been used in the case of solutions and supercooling limits in the case of melts to calculate the free energy barrier of nucleus formation, which is ultimately responsible for the release of supersaturation. It is found that both in case of solution as well as in melts, the maximum free energy is of the same order, i. e., 10^6 cal. per g. mol.

The relation between the tendency of spontaneous crystallisation, as measured by $T_s - T$, and the heat of solution of a particular solute has been discussed in various papers published by Chatterji and co-workers (this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 183; 1944, 21, 103; 1949, 26, 94). It is intended in the present communication to examine the same problem from the viewpoint of free energy barrier of nucleation.

The maximum energy of nucleation is given by the following relation of Kauzmann (*Chem. Rev.*, 1948, 43, 253)

$$F_{\max} = \frac{32\sigma^3}{H^2} \left(\frac{T_m}{T_m - T} \right)^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where H = heat of fusion per c.c., T_m = melting point and σ is the interfacial tension at the crystal-liquid interface.

A similar expression can be obtained for supersaturated solutions by proceeding in a similar manner. Suppose that a cubical crystallite is suspended in the solution phase. Let its volume be V and therefore its surface area becomes $\sigma V^{\frac{2}{3}}$. Let us also suppose,

H_o = heat of solution per c.c.

S_o = entropy of crystallisation/c.c.

T_s = saturation temperature

σ = interfacial tension.

The free energy of crystallite at any temperature T ($T < T_s$) is given by the following equation,

$$F = (TS_o - H_o)V + 6\sigma V^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad \left(\dots \dots \dots \right) \quad (2)$$

But

$$S_o = \frac{H_o}{T_s}$$

Hence

$$F = \left(\frac{T - T_s}{T_s} \right) H_o V + 6\sigma V^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

The above function passes through a maximum value as V is increased. In order to find out the maximum value of F , the function is differentiated with respect to V . Thus we have,

$$\frac{dF}{dV} = \left(\frac{T - T_s}{T} \right) H_o + 6. \frac{2}{3} \sigma V^{-\frac{1}{3}} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

For the function to be maximum,

$$\frac{dF}{dV} = 0$$

or

$$\left(\frac{T - T_s}{T} \right) H_o = 4 \sigma V^{-1/3}$$

Hence,

$$V = \frac{64 \sigma^3}{H_o^3} \left(\frac{T_s}{T_s - T} \right)^3 \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Therefore, free energy is maximum when V has the above value.

Now, substituting the value of V in (2), we have

$$F_{\max} = \frac{32 \sigma^3}{H_o^3} \left(\frac{T_s}{T_s - T} \right)^3 \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Since the data for the heat of solution of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents are rare, we have to make use of the heat of fusion. In ideal cases the heat of fusion is equal to the heat of solution. But systems of non-electrolytes are usually non-ideal, the factor fL_f is put equal to heat of solution where ' f ' is an empirical factor suggested by Mortimer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1416; 1923, **45**, 633) depending upon the relative internal pressure of the solvent and solute. Hence, substituting fL_f for heat of solution, we obtain

$$F_{\max} = \frac{32 \sigma^3}{f^3 L_f^3} \left(\frac{T_s}{T_s - T} \right)^3 \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where L_f = heat of fusion per c.c. There is justification for introducing ' f ' since the observed values of limits of supersaturation and the values calculated by taking into account the factor, are almost identical (cf. this *Journal*, 1949, **26**, 283).

The equations (1) and (7) have been used by us for calculating the maximum energy required in forming the nucleus at the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation. In the case of supersaturated solutions, the values of $T_s - T$ as experimentally observed by Chatterji and Bose (this *Journal*, 1949, **26**, 94) have been used in equation (7), whereas for melts the values of $T_m - T$ have been experimentally determined by a method similar to that used by Chatterji and co-workers for supersaturation (*loc. cit.*). Only it has been assumed that the surface tension at the solid-liquid interface is equal to the surface tension of melts. This assumption has been used by Chatterji and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) in calculating the radius of stable crystal nucleus, but since the values of ' r ' are in agreement with the values determined by other independent methods, the assumption is not unjustified.

TABLE I

 $F_{\max}$ for supersaturated solutions of solid non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents at 30°.

Solute.	Solvent.	$T_s - T$ *	H_f (cal./g.mol.)†	σ ‡	f ‡	$F_{\max}$ /g. mol
Naphthalene	Aniline	9.0	4557	40 ergs	1.46	1.31×10^6
"	Methyl alcohol	4.2	"	"	3.35	1.23×10^6
"	Ethyl alcohol	4.5	"	"	2.90	1.44×10^6
"	Acetic acid	7.0	"	"	1.95	2.04×10^6
"	Hexane	7.7	"	"	1.80	1.34×10^6
"	n-Butyl alcohol	13.5	"	"	1.01	1.46×10^6
"	n-Propyl alcohol	8.0	"	"	1.18	3.14×10^6
"	Nitrobenzene	12.9	"	"	1.07	3.82×10^6
"	Toluene	6.0	"	"	1.07	6.25×10^6
"	Chlorobenzene	4.0	"	"	1.06	6.81×10^6
p-Dibromobenzene	Benzene	15	3326	"	1.01	7.64×10^6
"	Bromobenzene	9.0	"	"	1.01	1.44×10^6
m-Dinitrobenzene	Bromobenzene	23.0	3998	52	1.01	3.18×10^6
"	Benzene	10.5	"	52	1.01	5.21×10^6
Anthracene	Benzene	8.0	6639	40	1.00	1.30×10^6
Benzoic acid	Benzene	8.0	4132	"	1.31	1.99×10^7

*The values of $T_s - T$ have been taken from the paper of Chatterji and Bose (*loc. cit.*)

† The values of heat of fusion and surface tension have been taken from International Critical Tables.

‡ For internal pressures see Glasstone ("Recent Advances in General Chemistry", 1936, p. 265) also Mortimer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 633).

The values of $F_{\max}$ calculated for a large number of systems are of the order 10^6 cal./g. mol. both in the melts and supersaturated solutions. In spite of the fact that $F_{\max}$ involves the cubes and the squares of various factors, the values are of the same order. However, it does not imply that crystallisation must necessarily occur when $F_{\max}$ is crossed, since other factors are also involved in crystal nuclei formation.

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